

and may be used for local application in the form of powder or ointment provided further studies indicate absence of toxicity following local application.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. D. R. Arora, Department of Microbiology, Medical College, Rohtak, for biological screening and to Head of the Chemistry Department, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak, for facilities.

References

1. J. MOHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 243; J. MOHAN and G. S. R. ANJANEYULU, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1987, **61**, 547; J. MOHAN, G. S. R. ANJANEYULU and KIRAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 346; J. MOHAN, G. S. R. ANJANEYULU, P. VERMA and K. V. S. YAMINI, *Indian J. Chem.*, in the press.
2. H. NAKAHARA, T. ISHIKAWA, Y. SARAI, T. KONDO and S. MITSUBASHI, *Nature (London)*, 1977, **266**, 165.

Further Chemical Investigation of

Murraya exotica

A. K. DEY, B. R. BARIK and T. BHAUMIK

Chemical Research Unit, C.C.R.A.S.,
Department of Chemistry, University College of Science,
92 A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

and

P. BHATTACHARYA*

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute,
93/1 A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 20 June 1989, revised 1 December 1989,
accepted 8 December 1989

PREVIOUSLY we reported the structure of several coumarins, flavones and cinnamic acid derivatives from *Murraya exotica*¹⁻³. Further chemical investigation reveals the presence of another coumarin (1) from the leaves of *M. exotica*.

Dried and powdered leaves of *M. exotica* (1.5 kg) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet for 36 h. The solvent was then concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Compound 1 was isolated from the chloroform eluate as light yellow crystalline solid, C₁₅H₁₄O₄ (M⁺ 258), m.p. 135–37°; [α]_D²⁵CHCl₃ = ±0°; soluble in alkali giving a yellow solution from which it could be regenerated by acidification indicating the presence of a δ -lactone; λ_{\max} 323, 236 and 214 nm (characteristic of 7-oxygenated coumarin)⁴; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1740–1725br (C=O), 1660, 1618 and 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (300 MHz; CDCl₃) 10.15 (1H, s, CHO), 7.57 (1H, d, J 9.5Hz, C-4), 6.13 (1H, d, J 9.5Hz, C-3), 7.37 (1H, d, J 8.6Hz, C-5), 6.82 (1H, d, J 8.6Hz, C-6), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.36 (3H, s, C-2'-CH₃) and 1.71 (3H, s, C-2'-CH₃).

The physical data of the compound was found to be identical with Murralongin which was previously assigned as 2 by Talapatra *et al.*⁵ and revised recently by Imani *et al.*⁶ as 1 by X-ray crystallography. Our analysis of ¹³C nmr spectral data of the compound corroborates the revised structure 1 of the molecule.

The data presented below exhibit that the observed chemical shifts of the two olefinic carbons of the isoprenyl side chain of murralongin are in better agreement with the values calculated⁷ for these two carbons of the structure 1 than those of 2. The chemical shifts assigned to different carbons are shown around 1.

Ph	1'	2'	CH ₃	Ph	1'	2'	CH ₃
	C	=	C		C	=	C
H ₃ C			CHO	OHC			CH ₃
Calo. (δ)			Observed (δ)				Calc. (δ)
C-1', 151.20			129.10				198.10
C-2', 188.10			152.55				146.20

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. (Mrs) A. Chatterjee, Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University, for her interest in the work and to Mr. S. K. Chatterjee, C.R.U., Calcutta for secretarial assistance. The authors also thank Director, C.C.R.A.S., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. B. R. BARIK, A. K. DEY, P. C. DAS, A. CHATTERJEE and J. N. SHOOLERY, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 792.
2. B. R. BARIK, A. K. DEY and A. CHATTERJEE, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 2273.
3. B. R. BARIK and A. B. KUNDU, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 3319.
4. D. P. CHAKRABORTY and S. K. CHAKRABORTY, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1961, **24**, 15.
5. S. K. TALAPATRA, L. N. DUTTA and B. TALAPATRA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1973, 5005.
6. F. IMANI, T. KINOSHITA, A. ITAI and U. SANKAWA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1986, **34**, 3978.
7. E. PRETSCH, T. OLERC, J. SEIBI and W. SIMON, "Tables of Spectral Data for Structural Determination of Organic Compounds", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1983, C95.